

LESSON PLAN EXAMPLE OF *INTEGRATED-LEARNING EXPERIENCES*

NOTES:

1. By integrated-learning experiences it is meant integrating theory and practice.
2. This example was created for the [Irish Leaving Certificate Physical Education Curriculum](#). However, we encourage you to adapt the idea to your own context.
3. By 'single class' it is meant 60-minutes class, by 'double class' it is meant 120-minutes class.
4. For a more comprehensive understanding of Integrated Learning Experiences in the Irish context, we recommend readers to refer to:

[Scanlon, D., Ni Ghlionn, C., Byrne, J. & MacPhail, A. \(2023\) *Integrated learning experiences in examinable physical education: A co-constructed teaching template, Physical Education Matters, 62-67.*](#)

Department of
Physical Education
and Sport Sciences

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A sample week unit (1 single and 2 doubles)

<p>Strand(s) and topic(s) in focus</p>	<p>Strand 1: Towards optimum performance</p> <p>Topic 1: Learning and improving skill and technique,</p> <p>Topic 2: Physical and psychological demands of performance,</p> <p>Topic 3: Structures, strategies, roles and conventions,</p> <p>Topic 4: Planning for optimum performance,</p>	<p>Strand 2: Contemporary issues in physical activity</p> <p>Topic 8: Technology, media and sport,</p> <p>Topic 9: Gender and physical activity</p>
<p>How many topics / learning outcomes are to be addressed?</p>	<p>1.2 Analysing skill and technique - analyse selected skills and techniques from the following perspective: biomechanical (planes and axes, levers)</p> <p>2.2. Health-related fitness - define the components of health-related fitness: muscular endurance and strength.</p> <p>2.3. Performance-related fitness - define the components of performance-related fitness: power and speed.</p> <p>3.3 Safe practice - demonstrate safe practice in approaches to training, performance and the organisation of physical activity events.</p> <p>4.2 Methods of analysis - skill and technique; use a selection of tools, including video and analysis software to analyse their own and others' performances; compare their personal performance to that of a more skilled/ model performer identify four areas from their performance which require further development.</p> <p>8.1 The impact of technology on sport and physical activity - evaluate the role of technology in the analysis of training and evaluation of sporting performance.</p> <p>8.2 Media in sport - examine the role of the media in maintaining gender stereotypes of men and women in sport</p> <p>9.2. Gender, media and body image - debate how media representations of the body may impact on both young men's and young women's participation in physical activity and sport</p> <p>9.3. Gender socialisation and its impact on physical activity participation - examine how social regulation of the body has impacted and continues to impact on the participation of both men and women in physical activity and sport.</p>	

Day 1 (single class)

Lesson plan		
Related learning outcomes		
<p>1.2 Analysing skill and technique - analyse selected skills and techniques from the following perspective: biomechanical (planes and axes, levers)</p> <p>4.2 Methods of analysis - skill and technique; use a selection of tools, including video and analysis software to analyse their own and others' performances; compare their personal performance to that of a more skilled/ model performer identify four areas from their performance which require further development.</p> <p>3.3 Safe practice - demonstrate safe practice in approaches to training, performance and the organisation of physical activity events.</p>		
Learning intentions	Success Criteria	Assessment
<p>LI1 Students will be able to analyse the plans, axes and levers of the following exercises: squat, walking lunge, bench press, jumping jack, plank, and push ups.</p> <p>LI2 Students will be able to perform the squat, walking lunge, bench press, jumping jack, plank, and push-ups comparing their performance with a model (task card), in safe conditions.</p>	<p>SC1 I understand the plans, axes and levers of a squat, walking lunge, bench press, jumping jack, plank, and push up.</p> <p>SC2 I can safely perform a squat, walking lunge, press bench, jumping jack, plank, and push ups, and compare my performance with a model.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher Q&A on the different types of plans, axes and levers. Teacher observation on students' participation and performing correct techniques.
Resources		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 power rack 1 bench 4 barbells 		
Time	Teaching and Learning	Assessment
5'	Introduction	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the purpose of the lesson and the learning that will take place using the whiteboard. Some relational talk with students could be considered. • Share learning intentions and success criteria using the whiteboard. (LO 1.2, 3.3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher check students understanding by asking them to explain success criteria in their own words (e.g, what do we mean by 'safe practice'?, what do we mean by performing in safe conditions? What is the strongest lever?). Students shared their suggestions and note them in the whiteboard. • Students shared verbally their thoughts.
<p>30'</p>	<p>Development</p> <p>The gym is divided into 6 'stations'. In every station, students are provided with material (e.g., barbells, benches, etc.) and videos/task cards to experience the following exercises: squat, walking lunge, bench press, jumping jack, plank, and push-ups. <i>(Task cards should be with neutral representations* and clear instructions concerning technique, health and safety. To make it more relevant for students, we encourage the teacher to record their own video)</i> (LO 4.2)</p> <p><i>*For example:</i></p> <p>In groups of 4, students go to each station and practice the exercise following the task card in order to perform the skill and technique correctly. During the practice, each student has a role: 1 athlete, 1 health and safety, and 2 observers. (LO 3.3, 4.2)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher observation • Peer observation: working in groups, two students observe the athlete following the model and paying attention to their role card. • Task sheet

	<p>Every person of the group, experience each role during the practice of the station. Once everybody has practiced a station, each group have to complete a task sheet in which they have to analyse each exercise from a biomechanical perspective. (LO 1.2)</p> <p>This is repeated 6 times, so that all the groups can experience all the exercises.</p>	
<p>5'</p>	<p>Conclusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Back to home base to summarise the learning in this lesson. Promoting student voice to discuss success criteria. Students first discuss this on their teams and communicate to the class their considerations. (LO 1.2, 3.3, 4.2) • Introduce the focus of next lesson, and set the following homework: “look for pictures or videos or images of people performing the exercises they have been experiencing today (i.e., squat, walking lunge, bench press, jumping jack, plank, and pushups).” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students share verbally their thoughts. • Completed task sheets are collected.
<p>Reflection(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grows and glows of the lesson in terms of content and achieved SC. • Challenges to link the LOs. • Opportunities to link to other LOs. • Other. 		
<p>Changes for the next time:</p>		

Day 2 (double class)

Lesson plan		
Related learning outcomes		
<p>1.2 Analysing skill and technique - analyse selected skills and techniques from the following perspective: biomechanical (planes and axes, levers)</p> <p>4.2 Methods of analysis - skill and technique; use a selection of tools, including video and analysis software to analyse their own and others' performances; compare their personal performance to that of a more skilled/ model performer identify four areas from their performance which require further development.</p> <p>3.3 Safe practice - demonstrate safe practice in approaches to training, performance and the organisation of physical activity events.</p> <p>9.3. Gender socialisation and its impact on physical activity participation - examine how social regulation of the body has impacted and continues to impact on the participation of both men and women in physical activity and sport.</p>		
Learning intentions	Success Criteria	Assessment
<p>LI1 Students will be able to understand the plans, axes and levers, in order to analyse any type of exercise.</p> <p>LI2 Students will be able to perform the squat, walking lunge, bench press, jumping jack, plank, and push-ups, using videos to compare their performance with a model.</p> <p>LI3 Students will be able to understand how social rules can affect people's participation in different kinds of sports.</p>	<p>SC1 I can identify the different plans, axes and levers of human movement.</p> <p>SC2 I can perform squat, walking lunge, bench press, jumping jack, plank, and push-ups and compare myself to a model.</p> <p>SC3 I understand the relation between social rules and people's participation in sports.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher Q&A on the different types of plans, axes and levers. Exit ticket Teacher observation on students' participation and performing correct techniques. Teacher Q&A on social rules and its impact on sports participation.

Resources		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 power rack • 1 bench • 4 barbells • Mobile phones / video camera 		
Time	Teaching and Learning	Assessment
15'	<p>Introduction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short debriefing of the last lesson, the teacher gives feedback on their task sheets (biomechanical analysis), reinforcing their learning. (LO 1.2) • Introduction to the purpose of the lesson (connecting it with the last one), and the learning that will take place using the whiteboard. • Share learning intentions and success criteria using the whiteboard. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher check students understanding by asking them to explain success criteria in their own words (e.g. which are the plans and axes of movement? What is the strongest lever? What do we mean by 'social rule'?). Students shared their suggestions and note them in the whiteboard. • Students shared verbally their thoughts.
55'	<p>Development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students share pictures or videos of the models they found (homework from the last lesson). Then, students discuss what kind of people and bodies are being represented (e.g., are there women? What type of men/women are represented? Is there diversity in terms of body shapes and sizes?). The teacher relates the discussion with stereotypes and how these can affect or impact the participation of people in certain sports or activities. (LO 9.3) • The teacher provides models that represent diversity in terms of ethnic, gender, body shape, etc. With the aim to provoke reflection and challenge stereotypes. (LO 9.3) • The gym is, again, divided into the same 6 'stations'. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher observation • Peer observation: working in groups, two students observe the athlete following the model and paying attention to their role card • Video recording • Exit ticket

	<p>Every group (the same as in the last session), go to one station, practice each exercise, and video record it. The roles for today are: 1 athlete, 1 health and safety, 1 observer, 1 video recorder (see role cards).</p> <p>Once that every student has experienced all the roles in the same station, they analyse their performance using their videos and the model that the teacher has provided (model that represent diversity). All groups do the same in every station. (LO 4.2, 3.3, 9.3)</p>	
<p>10'</p>	<p>Conclusion</p> <p>Back to home base to summarise the learning in this lesson. Promoting student voice to discuss success criteria. Students first discuss this on their teams and communicate to the class their considerations. (LO 4.2, 3.3, 9.3)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduce the focus of next lesson, and set the following homework: “think if each of the exercises they have practiced (i.e., squat, walking lunge, press bench, jumping jack, plank, and push-ups) are related to muscular endurance, muscular strength or both, and why. Look in the media an example of sport that needs muscular strength, and another that needs muscular endurance, and bring the examples to the next lesson”. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students share verbally their thoughts.
<p>Reflection(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grows and glows of the lesson in terms of content and achieved SC. Challenges to link the LOs. Opportunities to link to other LOs. Other. 		
<p>Changes for the next time:</p>		

Day 3 (double class)

Lesson plan		
Related learning outcomes		
<p>2.2. Health-related fitness - define the components of health-related fitness: muscular endurance and strength.</p> <p>2.3. Performance-related fitness - define the components of performance-related fitness: power and speed.</p> <p>3.3 Safe practice - demonstrate safe practice in approaches to training, performance and the organisation of physical activity events.</p> <p>8.2 Media in sport - examine the role of the media in maintaining gender stereotypes of men and women in sport</p> <p>9.2. Gender, media and body image - debate how media representations of the body may impact on both young men's and young women's participation in physical activity and sport.</p> <p>9.3. Gender socialisation and its impact on physical activity participation - examine how social regulation of the body has impacted and continues to impact on the participation of both men and women in physical activity and sport.</p>		
Learning intentions	Success Criteria	Assessment
<p>LI1 Students will be able to understand the difference between muscular endurance and strength.</p> <p>LI2 Students will be able to understand the difference between power and speed, and how these performance-related components can affect the development of muscular endurance and strength in different exercises.</p>	<p>SC1 I know the difference between muscular endurance and strength.</p> <p>SC2 I understand the difference between power and speed.</p> <p>SC3 I know how power and speed affect the development of muscular endurance and strength.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher Q&A on the performance-related components and its affect to the development of muscular endurance and strength.
Resources		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 power rack • 1 bench • 4 barbells 		
Time	Teaching and Learning	Assessment
10'	<p>Introduction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the purpose of the lesson (connecting it with the last one), and the learning that will take place using the whiteboard. Share learning intentions and success criteria using the whiteboard. (LO 2.2, 2.3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher check students understanding by asking them to explain success criteria in their own words (e.g, what do we mean by muscular endurance and strenght?, what do we mean by power and speed?). Students shared their suggestions and note them in the whiteboard. • Students shared verbally their thoughts.
60'	<p>Development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students share the thoughts about muscular endurance and strength that they came up with, on their homework. Then, the teacher helps them understand the right answer and encourages them to think about how every exercise could be practised (in terms of power and speed) to develop endurance or strength. (LO 2.2, 2.3) <p>Based on the images that students found in the media (homework), the teacher encourages a brief reflection on how media (re-)produce gender stereotypes and the importance of understanding that everybody can practice any sport. (LO 8.2, 9.2, 9.3)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The gym is, again, divided into the same 'stations'. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher observation • Peer observation: working in groups, two students observe the athlete following the model and paying attention to their role card. • Video recording • Exit ticket

	<p>Every group (the same as in the last session), go to one station, and practice each exercise again. The roles for today are: 1 athlete, 1 health and safety, 2 observers (see role cards). However, instead of being focused just on technique, in the lesson students are asked to perform using different power and speed.</p> <p>Each group have a task sheet in which they have to discuss how power and speed affect their performance, as well as the development of muscular endurance and strength.</p> <p>All groups will do the same in every station. (LO 2.2, 2.3, 3.3)</p>	
10'	<p>Conclusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Back to home base to discuss their thoughts and 'findings' in relation to how speed and power affects not only the performance, but also how these elements might determine the development of muscular endurance or muscular strength. (LO 2.2, 2.3) • Finally, students will be asked to complete their team self-assessment forms in relation to, in what extend, they have achieved the success criteria and to articulate their decisions when asked. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students share verbally their thoughts. • Students will complete the team self-assessment forms to consider the achievement of success criteria
<p>Reflection(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grows and glows of the lesson in terms of content and achieved SC. • Challenges to link the LOs. • Opportunities to link to other LOs. • Other 		
<p>Changes for the next time:</p>		

Blank template

Lesson plan		
Related learning outcomes		
Learning intentions	Success Criteria	Assessment
Resources		
Time	Teaching and Learning	Assessment
Reflection(s):		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grows and glows of the lesson in terms of content and achieved SC. • Challenges to link the LOs. • Opportunities to link to other LOs. • Other. 		